

THE IMPACT OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS FOR ASSESSING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE ON LINGUISTIC AND LITERARY ANALYSIS

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Abstract: This article examines how international English language assessment standards (IELTS, TOEFL, CEFR) influence the processes of linguistic and literary analysis. These standards increase attention to the speech, lexical, grammatical and stylistic aspects of language. The article also considers the possibilities of using assessment systems for language learners and researchers, for analyzing literary texts, and their positive and negative aspects for language development.

Keywords: English, international assessment standards, linguistics, literary analysis, CEFR, IELTS, TOEFL

English is widely used around the world as a language of global communication and science. At the same time, international standards for assessing language competence are of great importance in the process of language learning. Systems such as IELTS (International English Language Testing System), TOEFL (Test of English as a Foreign Language) and CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) have a direct impact not only on determining the language level of the student, but also on linguistic and literary analysis.

International standards for language assessment increase the linguistic focus on grammar, phonetics, lexis and syntax. At the same time, they allow for a deeper study of the stylistic and semantic features of the language in literary analysis. This article systematically analyzes these effects.

The CEFR divides the language into levels such as A1, A2, B1, B2, C1 and C2 depending on the level of maturity. This system is aimed at assessing the student's speaking, listening, reading and writing skills. The main advantage of the CEFR is that

it determines the lexical and grammatical scope of the language at each level linguistically. The IELTS test is designed for studying academic and general English. The test is divided into five main components: listening comprehension, reading, writing, speaking, and lexical-grammatical knowledge. This standard is an important tool for determining grammatical correctness, stylistic coherence, and logical connections when analyzing literary texts [1].

TOEFL is mainly associated with academic English and is required for university admission. The linguistic aspects of the test help assess the student's semantic and syntactic knowledge.

International assessment systems require the student to speak grammatically correct and clearly. This increases accuracy in analyzing literary texts in the process of language learning. For example, the tasks used in the IELTS and TOEFL tests make the student sensitive to lexical and grammatical errors.

Linguistic analysis studies the syntactic and logical structure of the text. Since the CEFR and IELTS standards are based on assessing these aspects, the student develops the ability to construct complex sentences and maintain logical sequences.

Speaking and listening comprehension tests (IELTS and TOEFL) assess phonetic accuracy. This helps to take into account pronunciation and intonation in the process of linguistic analysis. International tests require the student to be stylistic and semantically accurate in analyzing the text. Therefore, in the process of language learning, literary analysis skills are developed, for example, determining the main idea of the text, understanding metaphors and idiomatic expressions.

TOEFL and IELTS writing tasks require the student to create a logical and structured text. This helps to learn the structural analysis of the text in literary analysis. The CEFR and other standards encourage contextual analysis of the text. The student learns to understand the content of the text, as well as to determine its connections with other texts.

International assessment standards play an important role in developing students' linguistic and literary analysis skills. Their positive aspects include: increasing grammatical accuracy and lexical richness of the language, developing syntactic skills,

helping to deepen understanding of literary texts, and creating internationally standardized criteria for language learning.

However, there are also negative aspects: in some cases, they can limit creativity and creative thinking, dependence on test formats prevents full expression of language, and does not fully cover the subtleties of literary and contextual analysis.

That is, IELTS or TOEFL preparation significantly increases the grammatical accuracy and lexical richness of students. At the same time, textbooks prepared on the basis of CEFR develop the skills of text analysis, taking into account stylistic and semantic aspects [4].

In conclusion, international assessment standards are important in learning English not only as a means of assessing language skills, but also as a factor in developing linguistic and literary analysis processes. Systems such as CEFR, IELTS and TOEFL increase the student's knowledge of grammar, lexis, syntax, phonetics, stylistics and semantics. At the same time, they help to form literary analysis skills, create the opportunity to analyze the text in a logical, contextual and structured way.

Literature:

1. Council of Europe. (2001). Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, teaching, assessment. Cambridge University Press.
2. Bachman, L. F., & Palmer, A. S. (2010). Language Assessment in Practice: Developing Language Assessments and Justifying their Use in the Real World. Oxford University Press.
3. Green, A. (2014). Exploring Language Assessment and Testing. Routledge.
4. Hughes, A. (2003). Testing for Language Teachers. Cambridge University Press.